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ATTITUDE OF HEALTH CARE WORKERS IN THE FIELD OF MENTAL HEALTH TO THEIR OWN HEALTH

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Ключевые слова: охрана психического здоровья, отношение к здоровью, врачи-психиатры, средний медицинский персонал

Abstract. Attitude of health care workers in the field of mental health to their own health. Chorna V.V., Makhniuk V.M., Khliestova S.S., Gumeniuk N.I., Chaika H.V. The article presents the results of theoretical and experimental studies of the degrees of value-motivational, cognitive, emotional, and behavioral components in health care workers of psychiatric health care facilities concerning their own health. The degree of risk and value of the personal hygiene of health care workers is determined. The main components and factors that affect the attitude to personal health are revealed. The awareness of the own emotional and cognitive experiences by the medical staff of psychiatric hospitals regarding the preservation and strengthening of their hygiene is analyzed. According to research on the value-motivational component of the medical staff of psychiatric health care facilities concerning the place of personal health in the hierarchy of values in life, it was found that own health is on the second place – 15.2% males, nursing staff (NS), 15.1% female- psychiatrists and females, NS, 14.8% - male- psychiatrists. In case of a deterioration of own health both women (35,6%), and men (35,5%) psychiatrists are engaged in self-treatment, the similar tendency is among females NS – 31,3%, males NS – 31, 5%), in 25.8% of cases female psychiatrists and in 23.1% of males NS do not pay attention to the disease at all, which leads to occupational diseases and chronic diseases. At the same time, occupational diseases among doctors and NS do not exceed 10% of the total number of occupational diseases in Ukraine due to self-medication and early treatment. Therefore, the statistics of occupational diseases of health workers in that field are underestimated compared to the actual ones.

Реферат. Отношение медицинских работников сферы охраны психического здоровья к собственному здоровью. Черная В.В., Махнюк В.М., Хлестова С.С., Гуменюк Н.И., Чайка А.В. В статье представлены результаты теоретического и экспериментального исследований степеней ценностно-мотивационного,

познавательного, эмоционального и поведенческого компонентов у медицинских работников психиатрических учреждений здравоохранения по вопросу: отношение к своему собственному здоровью. Определена степень риска и ценность личного здоровья медицинских работников. Раскрыты основные составляющие и факторы, которые влияют на отношение к личному здоровью. Проанализировано осознание собственных эмоционально-когнитивных переживаний медицинского персонала психиатрических учреждений здравоохранения по вопросу отношения к их собственному здоровью, его сохранения и укрепления. По результатам исследований ценностно-мотивационной составляющей у медицинских работников психиатрических учреждений здравоохранения в иерархии ценностей в жизни установлено, что личное здоровье, по мнению 15,2% мужчин – представителей среднего медицинского персонала (СМП), 15,1% женщин врачей-психиатров и женщин СМП, 14,8% мужчин врачей-психиатров, находится на втором месте. В случае ухудшения собственного здоровья 35,6% женщин и 35,5% мужчин врачей-психиатров занимаются самолечением, аналогичная тенденция и среди СМП (31,3% – женщины СМП, 31,5% – мужчины СМП). Не обращают внимание на болезнь женщины врачи-психиатры в 25,8% случаях и мужчины СМП в 23,1% случаях, что приводит к возникновению профессиональных заболеваний и хронических болезней. При этом профзаболевания среди врачей и СМП не превышают 10% от общего количества профзаболеваний по Украине, что объясняется самолечением и несвоевременным обращением. Поэтому статистические данные профессиональных заболеваний медицинских работников учреждений здравоохранения являются заведомо заниженными по сравнению с фактическими.

For the first time in 1986 the concept of "internal picture of health" (IPH) and "internal picture of disease" (IPD) – health in the conditions of illness was investigated and theoretically substantiated by Kagan V.Yu. The meaning of "internal picture of health", according to Kagan V.Yu., is a special attitude of a medical person to his own health, it is an awareness of the value and constant desire to preserve it [1].

In his works Berezovskaya R.A. determined that the concepts of "internal picture of health" and "attitude to health" are very close in meaning. IPH is formed in the early stages of life during the upbringing and socialization of the child. And any injuries, serious illnesses in childhood can change the health of an adult. Scientists Rudneva E.L. and Yanitsky M.S. argued that the value-motivational component of health is one of the important qualities associated with adaptation, personal identification and self-actualization in the modern medical, pedagogical and psychological literature [5].

In the course of their professional duties, medical professionals work in extreme, nervous and emotional conditions and face a constant risk to their health. Prolonged effects of traumatic factors lead to moral and emotional, mental, psychic exhaustion and depletion of individual resources without the possibility of their recovery. If a medical person does not care about the release of negative emotions, stress, signs of anxiety and depression, then the medical person develops pre-diseases, which turn into diseases [4, 6, 7].

Thus, in many countries around the world, the mental health of health professionals is a concern of the National Health Services of these countries. In the EU countries, surveys and tests are constantly conducted to identify changes in the mental and physical health of health workers [8, 9]. Ongoing

monitoring of the mental health of health professionals in European countries has prompted us to conduct a survey of psychiatric hospital health workers to assess their attitudes towards their own health.

The purpose of the study is to determine the value attitude of staff members of the regional clinical psychoneurological hospital to their own health and to determine the place of health in the hierarchy of values in life with the development of preventive measures to preserve and strengthen it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

The study involved 223 medical workers of the Municipal Non-Profit Enterprise "Vinnytsia Regional Clinical Psycho-Neurological Hospital named after academician O.I. Yushchenko, Vinnytsia Regional Council": of them – 189 women (84.7%) and 34 (15.3%) men, of which 25 were male doctors and 62 female doctors, nursing staff (NS) of the psychiatric units – 136 people, including 9 men and 127 women. The article compares the data obtained between doctors and NS of psychiatric profile and by gender.

The average age of the respondents – medical workers was 41.6 ± 2.8 years. Work experience in professional activities was 17.9 ± 3.4 years. The questionnaire "Attitude to health" by Berezovskaya R.A. was used in the study. [3]. Statistical processing of the study results was performed in the licensed standardized package "Statistica 6.1 for Windows" (StatSoftInc., Serial No. AGAR909E415822FA) and Excel-2010 with the calculation of the arithmetic mean, standard arithmetic mean error. The work also used the analysis of domestic and foreign scientific sources, bibliosemantic, analytical research methods [1, 3, 5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With the help of the questionnaire “Attitude to health” by Berezovskaya R.A. the evaluation of the value-motivational, cognitive, emotional and behavioral components of the attitude to health of the medical staff of the psychiatric hospital was carried out.

The value-motivational component determines the place of health in the individual hierarchy of terminal and instrumental values of the respondents.

Cognitive – the idea of health, which depends on age, gender, intelligence, education, physical qualities and knowledge of the main factors that have both negative and positive effects on human health.

The emotional component of a person is associated with a set of feelings of excitement, namely: joy, will, sympathy, peace, which is determined by individual psychological and individual typological characteristics of individuals.

The behavioral component is associated with the actualization of human activity, the direction of achieving goals which are subjectively significant [3].

To assess the value-motivational component of health care staff, a study was conducted to identify the place of personal health in the hierarchy of values in life among both female psychiatrists and female NS, and among male psychiatrists and male NS. According to the results of the study, the first place in the hierarchy of values in life is occupied by a happy family life (16.3% of male NS and 15.1% of male psychiatrists, 15.9% of female NS and 15.6% of female psychiatrists), in the second place – personal health (15.2% of male NS and 14.8% of male psychiatrists, 15.1% of female NS and female psychiatrists) ($p < 0.05$). Table 1 shows the results of the comparison of the value-motivation component between physicians and NS of psychiatric profile.

Table 1

The structure of the value-motivational component of medical staff to determine the place of personal health in the hierarchy of values in their lives, M±m

Groups	Value-motivational criteria of values in the life of medical staff						
	happy family life	health (personally)	independence, freedom	recognition of those around	interesting job (career)	presence of loyal friends	material well-being
Female psychiatrists	6.5±0.9	6.3±1.3	5.9±1.3	5.4±1.4	5.9±1.2	5.9±1.3	5.8±1.3
Female-NS	6.4±1.3	6.1±1.5	5.8±1.5	5.3±1.5	5.7±1.3	5.5±1.6	5.8±1.4
Male psychiatrists	6.1±1.19	6.8±1.08	6.0±1.11*	5.2±1.2	5.7±1.1	5.4±1.01*	5.8±0.84
Male -NS	6.7±0.7	6.2±1.09	6.0±1.0	4.9±1.6	5.8±1.6*	5.6±1.2	5.3±1.4

Note. * $p < 0.05$ significance of changes relative to the comparison group.

Independence (freedom) in the work of medical workers is necessary for further professional growth, for their career advancement, for a sense of self-realization and job satisfaction, to receive positive feedback from management staff, colleagues, patients. In independent work, medical workers show purposefulness, self-control, self-organization. This criterion is in the 3rd place and is more characteristic of men than women, being 15.0% in psychiatrists and male NS – 14.6% ($t=0.9$; $p < 0.05$). It is unfortunate, but it is a fact that pay for work is low, in the HCF so women and men from NS noted the need for material well-being – 14.2% and 14.1%, respectively ($t=0.05$; $p > 0.05$).

To determine the value-motivational component of the determinant of health, the next question for the medical staff in the questionnaire was: “What do you think you need to have to succeed in life?”, which has several options (Fig. 1).

According to the results of the cognitive component, it is established that for male-psychiatrists and female-psychiatrists "good education" is important for success – this is the opinion of 15.6% and 15.4% of these respondents and to achieve success in life, which is a psychological component of health, it is necessary to show their professionalism, meet the modern needs of society and world standards. Psychiatrists (15.4% of women and

15.2% of men) noted that to be successful you need to be healthy. In NS this figure is slightly higher, being 16.0% and 15.5% (men and women). Also, psychiatrists (15.7% of women and men) said that

success in life requires perseverance and hard work. When comparing doctors and NS, the cognitive component of the attitude to "good education" is 6.5+0.7 and 5.8+1.4, respectively ($t=3.4$; $p<0.0004$).

Fig. 1. The results of questionnaire of health professionals on ways to achieve success in life, %

Among the most important sources for obtaining information on improving and maintaining their health, the majority of health workers indicated to their fellow-medical professionals whom they trusted, in particular: 25.1% – female NS; 24.8% – male NS; 24.4% – female psychiatrists; 24.0% – male psychiatrists.

In addition, 23.3% of female psychiatrists and 22.7% of male psychiatrists believe that additional leading sources of health are popular science publications and books on medicine, when comparing doctors and NS – 5.5+1.4 and 4.7+1.9, respectively ($t=3.0$; $p<0.002$). Doctors are increasingly looking for information on the factors that affect health and seek new knowledge in the field of mental health. In the politicized society of Ukraine, psychiatrists trust the media the least: in 16.5% of cases – men, in 16.8% of cases – women (Fig. 2).

When comparing doctors and NS, the cognitive component of the attitude to the "media" is 3.9+1.7 and 4.5+1.8, respectively ($t= -2.0$; $p<0.05$).

The analysis of the data shows that the respondents are characterized by adequate awareness of information sources on mental health and a positive attitude to health and a healthy lifestyle.

To determine the factors that negatively affect health, the next question in the questionnaire was: "Which of the following factors do you think have the most significant impact on your health?". According to the results of the survey of all these options, psychiatrists identified the main factor – lifestyle: in 16.0% of cases among women and in 15.4% of cases among men (Fig. 3). When comparing physicians and NS – 6.2+1.2 and 5.9+1.4, respectively ($t=1.1$; $p>0.05$).

Fig. 2. Cognitive level of awareness of medical workers of psychiatric HCF concerning health from various sources of medical information, %

Fig. 3. The share of factors that have the greatest impact on health of medical workers, %

The main factor influencing health, according to the NS survey, is nutrition. This statement was in 15.2% of male and 15.1% of female NS. When comparing physicians and NS – 5.6+1.3 and 5.9+1.3, respectively ($t=-1.3$; $p>0.05$).

When asked to determine the factors that affect health, unanimous answers about the negative impact of environmental factors on health were among female psychiatrists and those of NS – 14.9%, the answers of men differed slightly and were as follows: 14.4% of cases among NS and in 13.9% of cases among psychiatrists, respectively ($t=-0.5$; $p>0.05$).

In the course of research of the emotional component in medical staff, which is associated with a complex of feelings of excitement, determined by individual psychological and individual-typological features, changes in well-being that cause changes in the emotional state were revealed in all groups.

For example, female psychiatrists and female NS, male psychiatrists and male NS feel upset about the deterioration of their health in 12.1%, 12.1%, 11.6% and 11.2% of cases, respectively. Female psychiatrists reported that they cared for their health in only 11.4% of cases. Male psychiatrists feel sorry for their health in 10.8% of cases. Male NS experience depression in their health in 11.6% of cases. 11.4% of female NS are anxious and nervous when their health deteriorates. Summarizing the responses of health professionals regarding their state of depression, anxiety and nervousness, we can conclude that these conditions are predictors of the development of emotional burnout. These results correspond to many world scientific studies on the factors of stressful working environment of medical workers [11, 13].

Regarding the behavioral component of psychiatric health care workers, which is associated with the actualization of health care workers, we note the level of commitment to a healthy lifestyle, evaluate their behavior, what exactly and how health care workers regularly do to support and strengthen their health. The results show that health professionals prefer active activities – exercise to maintain their health. The largest number of medical workers engaged in physical exercises is among female psychiatrists – 13.8%, among male psychiatrists – 13.0%. The nursing staff is less engaged in physical exercises: women – in 12.5% of cases, men – in 11.7%. When comparing physicians and NS of psychiatric profile 2.8+2.1 and 2.6+1.8, respectively ($t=0.6$;

$p>0.05$). Fewer physicians practice special health systems: 6.7% – among male NS and female NS; 6.3% – among female psychiatrists; 6.1% – among male psychiatrists. When comparing physicians and NS of psychiatric profile 2.3+1.9 and 2.3+1.8, respectively, this can be characterized as a statistically insignificant indicator ($t=0.02$; $p>0.05$). At the same time, in 13.8% of cases male NS do not have time for this, 13.3% of female psychiatrists, 11.7% of female NS and 11.0% of male psychiatrists do not have enough time for health improvement measures as well ($t=1.3$; $p>0.05$).

According to a survey of health workers on preventive measures to strengthen their health, it was found that the largest percentage of male NS exercise – 13.3%. Male psychiatrists follow a diet – in 10.7% of cases, take care of the regime – in 10.9% and are engaged in tempering – in 9.8%, respectively ($t=2.1$; $p<0.03$).

Among female NS, the highest rate of visits to doctors for prophylactic purposes is 9.4%, but among males this figure is the lowest – 7.8%. Both female psychiatrists and male psychiatrists avoid bad habits – in 13.8% and 13% of cases, respectively (Fig. 4). When comparing physicians and NS of psychiatric profile 3.3+2.01 and 3.5+2.0, respectively ($t=-0.6$; $p>0.05$).

When studying the behavior of medical staff in case of deterioration of their health, it was found that both women (35.6%) and men (35.5%) psychiatrists were engaged in self-medication, a similar trend was among NS – 31.3% of females, and 31.5% – males). It is unfortunate that in 25.8% of cases women psychiatrists and in 23.1% of men NS do not pay attention to the disease at all (Table 2) [4, 7].

Summarizing the results of our study, we can say that in the hierarchy of values in the lives of health professionals 62.9% of respondents choose a happy family life, 62.1% of all health professionals indicated that it is necessary to be healthy to achieve success, 56.0% – improving their material well-being, because all these factors affect their social protection and material security, and hence – the quality of their medical services in HCF.

According to the results of scientific research in different countries of the world, the rate of burnout among medical staff ranges from 31.4% to 85.8%, herewith in Ukraine among the medical staff of psychiatric hospitals: psychiatrists, psychotherapists, psychiatrists-narcologists, this figure is higher and ranges from 73% to 89.3% [2, 6, 10].

Health workers of the HCF are exposed to a complex of unfavorable occupational factors of the in-hospital (production) environment, which leads to the development of various occupational diseases and their chronicity.

Many scientific papers by authors from around the world point out that poor mental health among

doctors, NS is a global phenomenon. High rates of mental illness are more common in female-doctors, in NS and junior medical staff whose experience does not exceed 10 years, which requires the introduction of measures of early diagnosis and timely treatment [12, 14, 15].

Fig. 4. Results of the questionnaire of health care workers of psychiatric HCF on preventive measures to strengthen their health,%

In order to improve the attitude of health workers of psychoneurological hospitals to their own health and to prevent the development of occupational diseases and early diagnosis of somatic diseases, the following measures are proposed:

1. Improving the material and technical base of psychiatric health care facilities by creating the best production conditions for medical workers, catering for medical staff, implementation of measures for early diagnosis and timely treatment, improvement of treatment and prevention work.

2. It is necessary to oblige the medical staff of the HCF to be responsible for passing medical examinations to prevent the occurrence of occupational diseases and early diagnosis of the disease, to use sanatorium treatment and rehabilitation.

3. Introduction of complex psychohygienic work with the formation of individual and social ideas of medical workers about their health. Systematic trainings, lectures, conferences, a powerful advertising and information campaign in the media (commercials, programs) on the issue of a healthy lifestyle.

Table 2

**Behavioral reactions of health workers to the deterioration of their health
(according to the results of the questionnaire), M±m**

Group	Reactions of health workers to the deterioration of their health			
	try not to pay attention to the disease	take action	seek advice	other
Female psychiatrists	3.8+1.8	5.2+1.5	3.8+1.9	2.8+1.9
Female NS	3.9+1.2	4.9+1.4	3.7+1.09	3.9+1.04
Male psychiatrists	3.7+1.8	5.1+1.3	3.6+1.8	2.6+1.2
Male NS	2.7+1.6	3.8+1.8	3.1+1.9	5.0+0

Note. Can be characterized as statistically insignificant ($p>0.05$).

CONCLUSIONS

1. In the hierarchy of value-motivational component of health workers in the first place is the desire to have a happy family life – 62.9%, in second place – the desire to succeed and the need to be healthy – 62.1%, in third place is independence (freedom) in work – 58.3%, which is necessary for medical workers for further professional growth, a sense of self-realization and occupational satisfaction, receiving positive feedback from management, colleagues, patients. In independent work, medical workers show purposefulness, self-control, self-organization. This criterion is typical for most psychiatrists – 15.0% and male NS – 14.6%.

2. Psychiatrists have determined the main factor on which the state of health depends is “lifestyle” – 16.0% of women and 15.4% of men, in NS the main factor – “nutrition” (15.2% – men, 15.1% – women).

3. Emotional component: 11.4% of women psychiatrists take care of their health, 10.8% of men psychiatrists feel regret and 11.6% of male NS feel depressed when their health deteriorates. 11.4% of women NS feel anxious and nervous when their health deteriorates, which is a predictor of emotional burnout.

4. Assessing the behavioral component of health workers to the deterioration of their health, it was found that in the case of deterioration of their own health both women (35.6%) and men (35.5%) psychiatrists self-medicate. (women NS – 31.3%, men NS – 31.5%) ($p>0.05$). In 25.8% of cases female psychiatrists and in 23.1% of cases male NS do not pay attention to the disease at all, which leads to occupational diseases and chronic diseases.

Conflict of interests. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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